

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF WOVEN FLAX/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This research deals with natural fibre flax composites and hybrid composites made from flax and glass fibres. Understanding the fatigue performance of natural fibre composites is critical in order to increase their current use. Current literature in this area is mostly limited to natural fibre composites with nonwoven reinforcements. This experimental research examines the tension-tension fatigue of three different woven flax/epoxy composites, for which two of them are prepreg-based and the other is manufactured using the VARTM process. Two hybrid composites containing both glass and natural fibres are also considered. The resulting fatigue performance has shown the potential natural fibres to be implemented in load-bearing applications. The results suggest that minimizing the crimp in the yarns is a major concern in order to increase the resistance to fatigue damage. The two hybrids of flax/glass/epoxy were manufactured using the same VARTM process. They were examined to see if the fatigue stability of flax fibre is extendable to its hybrids. The results show that an increase in strength is possible, while maintaining similar fatigue behaviour as the plain flax/epoxy composites. Crimp of woven fabric plays an important role in the damage mechanism and its induced intensity on the composite laminate during fatigue loading. Increase in the overall strength properties of the laminate is possible by introduction of glass fibres to the laminate. Hybridization between flax and glass fibre is only desirable in the scenario when the resulting hybrid has better specific properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural fibres have some interesting physical and mechanical properties (low density, good specific mechanical properties, vibrational damping and low abrasion) combined with their environmental-friendliness (biodegradability and renewability), along with low production costs. Thus, they are promising for many applications [1]. Currently, this class of fibres is primarily being used to reinforce composite materials in non-load bearing structures such as interior automotive components [2]. The main limiting factors in extending their use to load-bearing applications are (for certain fibres) their limited strength, batch-to-batch variability, adhesion issues with certain matrices, as well as a limited understanding of their long-term hydrothermal and fatigue performance. Fatigue behaviour is not understood well and is the focus of this study.

There have been some studies that have addressed the fatigue behaviour of cellulose-based fibre-reinforced composites. Gassan *et al* [3] carried out a pioneering study on the effect of maleic anhydride-polypropylene (MAH-PP) coupling agent on the flexural and fatigue strength of woven

jute/polyester composites. They found a 40% increase of flexural strength in a load-increasing fatigue test as well as a less drastic progression of damage with the application of the coupling agent [3]. A later study by Gassan looked at the effect of fibre architecture (unidirectional and woven), fibre type, interphase strength and resin type on fatigue properties [4]. Natural fibres with higher modulus and strength as well as a unidirectional architecture had better fatigue life and greater resistance to damage initiation. Liang et al. [5] compared the fatigue life of flax and glass fibres in an epoxy matrix. Samples made by compression moulding were tested under tension–tension fatigue loading. Cross-ply $[0/90]_{3S}$ specimens of flax fibre laminates had lower fatigue endurance than glass fibre laminates, but angle-ply $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ flax fibre reinforced polymers showed better specific fatigue endurance (weight-normalized fatigue strength) than glass fibre laminates. Moreover, flax fibre composites showed more stable cyclic performance than glass fibre composites by exhibiting less permanent deformation. Shahzad studied a hemp/glass mat hybrid composite in fatigue and found that introduction of glass fibres into the hemp composite increased the fatigue life [6].

Although the above studies have shown the potential of bio-based composites in terms of fatigue, they often represent more basic types of these materials (e.g. nonwoven fabrics and/or low performance resin systems). The current study aims to look at higher end bio-based composites by considering flax/epoxy composites and utilizing woven flax fabrics. According to Dittenber and GangaRao [7], who have compared various natural fibres and overviewed their properties, flax fibres offer the best blend of lightweight, low cost and high strength and stiffness for structural applications. Hence, two prepreg based flax/epoxy laminates, that have shown potential for use in load-bearing applications [8], and a VARTM manufactured flax/epoxy laminate with similar static behaviour were considered in this study. Hybridization with glass fibre in two different volume ratios was also considered to assess the fatigue behaviour of natural/synthetic hybrids, given the desirable fatigue performance of bio-based composites. This paper presents a description of the sample manufacturing followed by the results from tension-tension fatigue testing. Finally, a discussion is presented with some insight into critical issues that affect the fatigue life of the material systems studied.

2 SAMPLE MANUFACTURING

2.1 Materials

Two prepreg systems based on twill-weave flax fabrics with areal weights of 200 g/m² and 550 g/m² were supplied by the prepreg manufacturer Lineo NV (Belgium). Both composites employed the same epoxy resin system (Huntsman LY5150 and XB 3471 hardener) and the fabrics were treated with a patented sizing process prior to impregnation (Patent No. US8080288). The flax fibre used in the VARTM process was provided by JB Martin Ltd (Canada) in a twill-weave fabric form with an areal weight of 224 g/m². Data on the three flax-epoxy systems are provided in Table 1. The plain weave E-glass with areal weight of 205 g/m², which was used to create the hybrid laminates was provided by Bell Helicopter, a Textron Company. The matrix system used in the VARTM process was an 820-epoxy resin laminating system with 834-hardener, from CASS polymers.

2.2 Processing

The prepreg-based samples were manufactured in an autoclave by standard vacuum bagging techniques with incorporation of a caul plate (manufacturing details in a previous paper [9]). Initial experiments revealed that a pressure of 3 bars resulted in an acceptable void content of less than 1% for the 550 g/m² system. However, for the 200 g/m² system the required amount of pressure for an acceptable void content was beyond the capacity of the autoclave. Therefore, the same pressure of 3 bars was selected for both systems for consistency. Unlike 224 g/m² and 200 g/m² fabric systems, 550 g/m² fabric had huge crimp disparity between its warp and weft fibre bundles. To assure similar bi-directional properties, ply sequence of $[0/90/0]$ was chosen for this material system.

The resin infusion based samples were manufactured using a standard VARTM process. The flax fabric was dried for 4 hours at 140°C followed by a 10 hours hold under vacuum. Five layers of dried

and debulked fabrics in the 0° direction were placed under the cavity and the degassed resin was infused inside the fabric at 0.85 bars. Afterwards, when the fibres were fully impregnated, the pressure was increased to 1 bar causing the excess resin to bleed out, and maximum possible fibre volume fraction was achieved. For full cure, the laminate was left under full vacuum pressure for 48 hours.

The volume fraction was calculated based on the indirect method of calculation of the fibre content as in Equation 2, where W_{ff} is the fibre weight fraction of flax fibres calculated from Equation 1 based on n , W_f and W_c which are the number of flax fibre layers used in the laminate, the areal weight of the flax fabric and the average weight per unit area of the composite respectively. Other parameters of Equation 1 are ρ_c the density of the corresponding laminate and ρ_f the density of the flax fibre assumed to be 1.498 g/cm³. The void content was measured using optical microscopy via digital image processing. It is generally agreed that regardless of the void disparity in the laminate, any void content below 1% of the gross volume is considered as an acceptable amount of voids.

$$W_{ff} = n \frac{W_f}{W_c} \quad (1)$$

$$v_f = \frac{\rho_c W_{ff}}{\rho_f} \quad (2)$$

To study the effect of hybridization between flax fibres (F) and glass fibres (G) on their fatigue performance, two different hybrid compositions were considered. All laminates were five layers of woven fabric aligned according to their warp direction, with different stacking sequences creating different hybrids. The hybrid laminates studied were [F₂/G/F₂] and [G/F₃/G]. As for the [G/F₃/G] laminate, the motivation was previous studies done on natural/synthetic hybrid composites that have reported better impact resistance [10] and increase in the tensile and flexural strength [11] when stronger synthetic fibres were placed at the outer layers. Hybrids were manufactured using the same VARTM technique as the plain flax/epoxy laminate. The schematic of the two different hybrids can be seen in Figure 1 with selected material properties shown in Table 2.

Areal density	200 g/m ²	550 g/m ²	224 g/m ²
Fabric images			
Selected ply sequence ^a	[0 ₆]	[0/90/0]	[0 ₅]
Resin mass content (%) ^[9]	52.1±1.8	46.8±2.0	0π
Warp crimp (%) ^[9]	1.2±0.1	2.1±0.5	1.6±0.6
Weft crimp (%) ^[9]	1.6±0.1	7.9±0.7	1.7±0.6
Yarn Linear weight ^b (Tex)	104	385	230
Yarn twist ^c (twists/m)	452±98	138±39	42±3.6
Fibre volume fraction (%) ^[9]	34.3±0.4	42.3±0.3	31.1±0.7
Void content (%) ^[9]	3.7 ± 1.1	0.2±0.1	0.2±0.1

^a where 0 and 90 represent warp and weft directions respectively.

^b from textile specifications.

^c measured by image analysis and calculated from $TPM = \tan\beta / \pi D$ using 10 samples where Beta is the twist angle and D is the diameter of the yarn.

Table 1. Selected properties of studied flax/epoxy systems (± standard deviation).

2.3 Sample Preparation

Following the laminate manufacturing, the samples were cut and end tabs were bonded. The tab material was woven E-glass/epoxy prepreg resulting in an end tab thickness of around 1.6 mm.

Figure 1. Two different flax/glass hybrid composites considered (G: glass fabric, F: flax fabric).

	$[F_2/G/F_2]$	$[G/F_3/G]$
Laminate areal density (kg/m^2)	3.05 ± 0.26	2.48 ± 0.04
Laminate density (kg/m^3)	1.24 ± 0.02	1.29 ± 0.02
Flax fibre volume fraction (%)	26.2 ± 2.20	24.9 ± 0.38
Glass fibre volume fraction (%)	3.2 ± 0.26	8.1 ± 0.12
Total fibre volume fraction (%)	29.4 ± 2.47	33.0 ± 0.50

Table 2. Selected properties of cured flax/glass/epoxy hybrid laminates (\pm standard deviation).

3 TENSION-TENSION FATIGUE TESTING

Static tensile mechanical tests were first conducted based on ASTM D3039 standard. 5 tests per data point were chosen. A summary of laminate tensile properties is presented in Table 3 and Table 4.

	200 g/m^2	550 g/m^2	224 g/m^2
$\sigma_{\text{ult},x}$ (MPa)	106 ± 2.9	105.9 ± 6.6	112.2 ± 2.1
$\epsilon_{\text{ult},x}$ (%)	1.68 ± 0.06	1.67 ± 0.08	1.37 ± 0.08
E_x (GPa)	9.41 ± 0.36	10.87 ± 0.44	12.16 ± 1.68

Table 3. Tensile properties of tested flax/epoxy laminates.

	$[F_2/G/F_2]$	$[G/F_3/G]$
$\sigma_{\text{ult},x}$ (MPa)	113 ± 8	139 ± 4
$\epsilon_{\text{ult},x}$ (%)	1.38 ± 0.06	1.49 ± 0.08
E_x (GPa)	12.4 ± 0.8	13.2 ± 1.5

Table 4. Tensile properties of tested hybrid laminates.

The tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted according to ASTM D3479 and E739 standard testing procedures using a sinusoidal waveform with peak stresses varying between 50% and 80% of the static strengths (Table 5), and were kept under cyclic load until total failure. A load ratio R (the ratio between the minimum and maximum applied stress) of 0.1 and frequencies (f) between 1 to 5 Hz were selected. The selection of the testing frequency was according to limitation imposed by self-heating behaviour of woven fabrics at different loading levels and testing frequencies studied by Liang

et al. [5]. An extensometer was installed on the specimens during the whole duration of the test, and the strain was recorded so that the evolution of Young's modulus could be determined. The test matrices are summarized in Table 5 and Table 6.

System	# of specimens	% of strength	R	f (Hz)
200 g/m ²	4, 6, 5, 5	80, 70, 60, 50	0.1	5, 5, 5, 5
550 g/m ²	3, 4, 3	80, 65, 50	0.1	5, 5, 5
224 g/m ²	4, 4, 3	80, 65, 50	0.1	1, 1.5, 3

Table 5. Test matrix for tension-tension fatigue testing of flax/epoxy laminates.

System	# of specimens	% of strength	R	f (Hz)
[F ₂ /G/F ₂]	4, 4, 4	80, 65, 50	0.1	1, 1.5, 3
[G/F ₃ /G]	4, 4, 4	80, 65, 50	0.1	1, 1.5, 3

Table 6. Test matrix for tension-tension fatigue testing of [F₂/G/F₂] and [G/F₃/G] hybrid laminates.

A summary of the fatigue results for flax/epoxy laminates can be seen in Figure 2(a). In this graph the actual data extracted from tested samples are presented, and linear curve fits were constructed using directives from ASTM standard E739-10 using the general Equation 3. In this equation A and B are fitting parameters and Y and X are dependent and independent variables respectively.

$$Y = A + BX \quad (3)$$

Due to the difference between the strength of the materials under study, the normalized S-N graph seen in Figure 2(b) was generated. In this graph the Y-axis is the percentage of the ultimate strength of the respective material. Using the same procedure, S-N curves of hybrid laminates were generated as in Figure 3(a). In addition to the hybrid laminates, S-N curve belonging to the 224 g/m² fabric is also presented on the same graph to better demonstrate the changes due to hybridization. To observe the performance of each material based on their weight, S-N curves were normalized based on the density of each laminate (Figure 3(b)). The effect of weight is important to investigate, since the low density of natural fibres is one of their biggest advantages giving them excellent specific properties. The strength normalized S-N curves are not presented for hybrid laminates since this type of normalization puts all linear fit lines on top of each other without providing any extra information.

The Young's modulus decay of the specimens during fatigue loading was also calculated, in order to assess the damage development rate in both systems. To better compare the two systems, a modulus ratio (*M*) was defined as in Equation 4, where *E_N* is the Young's modulus after *N* cycles and *E₀* is the initial modulus.

$$M = \frac{E_N}{E_0} \quad (4)$$

Figure 4(a) shows the evolution of *M* for the three different flax/epoxy laminates at a loading level of 80%, as a function of the normalized number of fatigue cycles (normalized to the actual number of cycles-to-failure for each specimen). The trends are similar for all loading levels, with the only difference being that the final value of modulus ratio (*M*) tended to be lower at lower loading levels. This is expected since as Shokrieh [12] explains, failure of the specimen under cyclic load takes place when the stiffness is reduced to a critical level. At lower stress levels, the critical value for stiffness is lower. Hence, more reduction in the modulus is possible as the specimen goes through more cycles. The same set of graphs was generated for the mentioned hybrids and their performance has been compared against the non-hybrid 224 m/g² flax/epoxy laminate (Figure 4(b)).

Figure 2. Compiled S-N curves for woven flax/epoxy composites: (a) absolute stress (b) normalized by strength.

4 DISCUSSION

The results of strength-normalized S-N curves of different flax/epoxy laminates with different areal weights indicate that there exists a noticeable gap between the 200 g/m² and the 550 g/m² material fatigue life despite the similarities in their quasi-static properties and fibre type (Table 3). Furthermore, despite the higher void content of 200 g/m² material system, and its lower fibre volume fraction compared to 550 g/m² (Table 1), the former laminate shows superior fatigue and damage mechanism performance. The S-N curve belonging to the 224 g/m² is located between the other two material systems with similar or better fatigue performance than 200 g/m² flax/epoxy laminate (Figure

3(b)). To understand the potential sources of these differences, close attention was paid to the physical characteristics of the fibres.

Figure 3. Compiled S-N curves for hybrid laminates composites: (a) absolute stress (b) Specific (density normalized) stress.

In general, damage progression in synthetic woven composites during fatigue loading can be subdivided into stages as described by Daggumati et al [13]. During the initial phase of cyclic loading, micro-damages in the form of cracks in weft yarns and random failure of weak load carrying fibres, and further propagation of these cracks into meta-delaminations causes sudden reduction in the stiffness of the laminate. Further failures of load carrying fibres followed by inter-ply delaminations

can cause the final failure. However, modulus decay curves, corresponding to the changes in stiffness of 200 g/m² and 224 g/m² materials, do not agree with the explained mechanism. In contrast, mentioned laminates show an increase in the modulus at early stages, known as the stiffening effect.

Figure 4. Modulus decay graphs for samples tested at loading level equal to 80% of their strength: (a) flax/epoxy non-hybrid laminates (b) hybrid laminates including data for 224 g/m².

Then, the modulus starts decreasing at a very slow rate. Baley [14] reports 60 to 80% increase in Young's modulus of flax fibres when loading axially. He explains this increase as the cellulose microfibrils wounded spirally with a certain winding angle that become straight after applying the load resulting in the increase of the stiffness of the fibres. The stiffening effect is less prominent in a

flax/epoxy laminate since epoxy resin limits this effect. Re-orientation of the misaligned fibres in the visco-elastic matrix under tension can be another reason for the stiffening effect. Surprisingly, the 550 g/m² flax/epoxy laminate does not show any stiffening effect. A different damage mechanism of this material system is the main source of this dissimilarity. Looking at Figure 5(a) and (b), which are obtained via optical microscopy from the middle cut of a 200 g/m² and 224 g/m² sample after cyclic loading at 80% loading level, no significant crack or any other damage sources are detectable. Comparing the tested and untested samples in Figure 5(a) shows the pre-existence of weft yarn cracks due to the resin starvation of the 200 g/m² prepreg system [8]. While the spacing between cracks have definitely grown, there is no sign of propagation of these cracks to cause meta-delaminations nor are there damaged warp yarns visible, which is in agreement with the modulus changes of this material. Looking a Figure 5(d), cracks propagated into resin rich areas and meta-delaminations close to the fracture are indications of greater damage intensity in the 550 g/m² fabric system. Continuous stiffness reduction seen in Figure 4(a) is due to the random creation of these cracks, which counters the stiffening effect of flax fibres. The difference between the fatigue lives of these materials is in accordance to their damage intensity.

The high tex (Linear yarn density) of warp and weft yarns of the 550 g/m² material system combined with the round shape of fibre bundles created the high crimp in this laminate as seen in Table 1 and Figure 5(c). High crimp of warp yarns results in an excessive stress in the warp and weft fibre interface due to the bigger sliding angle between the interlacing fibre bundles. Transverse and interfacial cracks seen Figure 5(d) are a consequence of the stress caused by the high crimp of this material system. Despite the comparable tex of the 224 g/m² material fibre bundles to those of the 550 g/m² material system, due to the more flat shape of the fibre bundles, the 224 g/m² material has lower crimp index. Consequently, transverse cracks and delaminations are in a much lower magnitude and are not detectable with optical microscopy. Higher number of cycles-to-failure and more stable stiffness of the 224 g/m² material are results of the lower crimp of this fabric. Furthermore, better fatigue of 224 g/m² compared to 200 g/m² at lower load levels despite the similar fabric crimp, comparing Figure 5(a) and (b), can be related to the lower sharp bends of fibres due to the flatter oval shape fibre bundles. Hence, we can conclude that better twisting techniques, which can result in flatter yet denser yarns, are favorable to the overall performance of the created laminate.

Figure 5. Microscopic damage analysis of the tested samples tested at 80% of their strength (scale bar represents 1 mm): (a) 200 g/m² (b) 224 g/m² (c) 550 g/m² to show the crimp (d) the cracked sections of the 550 g/m² laminate.

Referring to Figure 3(a), there is an overall improvement in the fatigue strength of hybrid laminates compared to the plain flax/epoxy laminate due to the introduction of stronger glass fibres. The enhancement is more prominent in the case of [G/F₃/G] hybrid laminate where two layers of flax fabric have been replaced by glass fibre fabrics. Comparing the fatigue life of hybrid laminates based on their density is essential, since it shows for the same weight which laminate has the highest strength (Figure 3(b)). The [F₂/G/F₂] hybrid laminate is no longer advantageous since the higher density of this hybrid has counter affected the strength improvement achieved by replacing a layer with glass fibre. On the other hand, [G/F₃/G] hybrid system maintains its superiority, which means in this case there is a good balance between the strength enhancement and increase in the density of the laminate.

Referring to the modulus changes of hybrid laminates in Figure 4(b), one can see that unlike the plain 224 g/m² flax/epoxy system, which is the same type of fabric used in the hybrid laminates, the stiffening phenomena in flax fibres has been counter balanced by the modulus reduction exhibited by glass fibre composites. The classical damage mechanism of woven glass fibres [15], resulting in a three-stage stiffness reduction, can be seen in hybrid laminates, but at a much smaller scale. The final modulus reported for woven glass fibre laminates after cyclic loading is about 85% of their original modulus [5], while in the case of hybrid laminates, it is 96% of its initial value, which is an indication of a more stable stiffness during the life span of the hybrid laminates.

Overall, adding stronger glass fibres to a flax fibre laminate results in a denser laminate with better strength and higher fatigue endurance. The resulting hybrid laminate also enjoys the stable fatigue performance of flax fibres resulted by the stiffening effect. Realignment of cellulose microfibrils after applying the load has been reported as the main source of this phenomenon [14]. With a correct design and right mixture, a hybrid laminate is achievable that enjoys a balance between the lightweight and stable fatigue life of flax fibres and the strength of glass fibres.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the tension-tension fatigue behaviour of three flax/epoxy systems that differed in fabric architecture. In addition to the single fibre-type composites, the effect of hybridization between flax and glass fibre on their fatigue behaviour was investigated. Comparing the fatigue life and damage intensity of different laminates has brought the following conclusions:

1. Crimp of woven fabric plays an important role in the damage mechanism and its induced intensity on the composite laminate during fatigue loading. Best fatigue performance is achieved when yarns create the least amount of crimp. This is possible when utilizing proper techniques to create flatter fibre bundles (or ideally, use a non-crimp fabric).
2. Increase in the overall strength properties of the laminate is possible by introduction of glass fibres to the laminate. While the change in the number of cycles to failure at normalized loading is subtle, the fatigue stability of flax fibres exhibited in low modulus reduction extends to its hybrids. Nevertheless, hybridization between flax and glass fibre is only desirable in the scenario when the resulting hybrid has better specific properties.

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